

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-comparative and correlational study aimed to determine the School Head's Competencies, Acquired Needs, and School-Based Management (SBM) Level of Practice in the Division of Iloilo during the school year 2018-2019. It surveyed 298 school heads of the different public schools in the Division of Iloilo who were chosen through random selection. They were grouped according to sex, educational background, position, and school level. The data required for this investigation were gathered through the use of a researcher-made questionnaire which was validated and tested for reliability. The researcher used weighted mean, standard deviations, t-test, one-way Analysis of Variance, and Pearson product-moment correlation to interpret the data. Findings revealed that the school heads in the Division of Iloilo possessed Very High competency in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities to perform their functions as educational leaders. Generally, they have vital needs for power, affiliation, and achievement. In terms of their SBM practices, they have the best ratings in governance and management, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources, but only have better practice in curriculum and instruction.

Keywords: *School Heads, Competencies, School-Based Management, Acquired Needs, Iloilo.*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education's continuous quest to improve the delivery of basic education services accelerated the achievement of Education for All (EFA) goals and led to the launch of a comprehensive sectoral reform package through the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA, 2010). The Department of Education officially adopted the BESRA on December 15, 2010, through Department of Education Order No. 118, s.2010. Through the BESRA, various policies on curricular reforms, teacher development, information systems, accountability systems, quality assurance, and organizational development were espoused by the Department of Education to strengthen the institutionalization of the School-Based Management (SBM) thrust.

At the time of the adoption of BESRA, SBM was already a decade-old management thrust of the Department of Education. It was institutionalized according to Republic Act 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 (Republic of the Philippines, 2001). With SBM, the government decentralized the management of schools by entrusting more responsibilities to the schools and providing greater autonomy and flexibility in their daily operations, resource management, and school development planning. In other words, power, authority, and resources are entrusted to the school heads and community members (Abulencia, 2012). As a result, stakeholders had to manage their affairs to sustainably improve educational service delivery. SBM was considered the key strategy to translate all the policies into relevant interventions that will enable the schools to cater to all their learners' needs.

SBM as a program is almost 20 years old as of this writing. However, the implementation seems static and unproductive, especially in the case of the Schools Division of Iloilo (DepEd SDO-Iloilo, 2018). According to the records of the SBM Unit, since 2013, only four elementary schools and two secondary schools out of the 1,163 schools in the whole Division managed to reach level 3 (BEST) in implementing SBM. Most schools are still at level 1 (GOOD) and level 2 (BETTER). Given this situation, the Department of Education officials and clientele became curious and concerned about the circumstances. The identification of the factors inhibiting and facilitating the program's implementation has been the concern of SBM units of the Department of Education. Considering that the SBM devolved the management and administration responsibilities to the school stakeholders, school heads became the prime target of the investigation. Being the lead implementer, school heads impact the implementation greatly. As such, it has become the researcher's scholarly interest to investigate if the qualities and characteristics of the school heads influence the implementation of SBM. Specifically, the researcher became interested in the possible impacts of the school head's competencies (knowledge, skill, abilities) and acquired needs (need for power, achievement, and affiliation) on the SBM level of practice in schools within the Division of Iloilo.

Through this scholarly exploration of the dynamics between the school head's competencies acquired needs and the SBM level of practice, the researcher expects to generate school-head-related explanations for the static and unproductive implementation of the SBM in the Division of Iloilo. After identifying the school head-related root causes, suggestions and recommendations for capacity and capability-building activities can be generated. Investigation into basic education programs such as

SBM is important because the Department of Education, as an institution, relies on scholarly work for its organizational and personnel development. As stipulated in DepEd Order No. 13, s.2015, DepEd must establish a systematic policy-making development process that requires research support for proposed programs, projects, and activities. Additionally, through the findings, the researcher, a school head, and an official Division SBM monitor/evaluator can gain valuable insights for improving her practice profession. As a secondary school principal, the researcher is required by DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2010 to comply with the National Competency-Based Standards for School Heads (NCBSSH). All of the seven components of NCBSSH are related to SBM. Through the study, the researcher gained insights to align her practice with the NCBSSH and SBM.

Moreover, as personnel of the Department of Education, with a professional teaching license, the researcher is required by RA 10912 or the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Law to pursue activities resulting in the improvement of her practice. Conducting research directly impacting the quality of a professional's performance of her education-related tasks/responsibilities is considered a CPD activity. All-in-all, the expected results, and discussion of the findings can greatly contribute to the overall improvement of the implementation of SBM in the Schools Division of Iloilo, as well as the personnel enrichment of the researcher, thus the conduct of this study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study utilized a descriptive-comparative and correlational research design. Its objectives included the production of generalizations regarding frequencies, levels, differences in school heads' profiles, competencies, acquired needs, and SBM practices. The descriptive-comparative research design was used to measure the difference in school heads' level of competence, acquired needs, and SBM level of practice. Furthermore, the descriptive-correlational research design was used to measure the relationship between the competency, acquired needs, and SBM practice of school heads in the Division of Iloilo, with the aid of researcher-made and adopted research questionnaires for appropriate data extraction.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents of this study included 298 respondents and were derived from 179 public secondary schools and 984 public elementary schools in the Division of Iloilo, Philippines. The respondents were school heads in secondary and elementary schools. A simple random sampling technique was employed to secure randomization and an equal chance of inclusion of respondents.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher secured necessary permits from the Schools Division Superintendent of Iloilo requesting to conduct the study to the school heads that were randomly chosen as respondents of the study. The test administration commenced after securing the validity and reliability of the research instruments. The same letter noted as approved by the Schools Division Superintendent was sent to different Public Schools District Supervisors in the Division of Iloilo to allow the researcher to proceed with the study in their respective districts. After all these requests were granted, the researcher finalized the data-gathering sessions' dates, times, and venues and administered the instrument to the elementary and secondary school heads. Since the respondents are 298 school heads from the Division of Iloilo, some questionnaires were distributed during the Schools Division Management Committee Conference. The researcher retrieved the accomplished instruments personally and expressed gratitude to the respondents.

Data Analysis Procedure. Upon receipt of the final version of the spreadsheet, the statistician executed the data analysis through software. The statistician ensured that the applicable statistical test was selected because answers to the different research questionnaires required the conduct of different statistical tests. The mean was used to establish the profile of the respondents in terms of their sex, school level, educational background, and position. To measure the significant difference in the level of competency, acquired needs, and SBM practice, a t-test was utilized for sex and school level as variables; analysis of variance was used when the school heads were grouped according to their educational background and position. Lastly, Pearson product-moment correlation was used to establish a relationship between the school heads' level of competency, acquired needs, and SBM practice.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents. Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the school heads' in the Division of Iloilo. When they are grouped according to sex, they dominate the school leadership females, 66% (n=198) of the respondents, and the remaining 34% (n=100) are male school heads.

Considering the school level, 83% of the school heads belong to elementary schools, and 37% are from secondary public schools. Regarding educational background, school heads with master's degrees comprise 47% of the respondents, 42% have earned doctorate units, and 11% possessed a doctorate. When considering the position of the school heads, 72% constitute the principal as their position, 6% are OIC-Assistant Principals, 14% are OIC-Head Teachers, and 8% of the respondents are Teacher-in-Charge.

Table 1. Profile of the respondents

Variable	n	%
Sex		
Male	100	34
Female	198	66
School Level		
Elementary	248	83
Secondary	50	37
Educational Background		
Master's degree	139	47
With doctorate units	125	42
Doctorate	34	11
Position		
Principal	216	72
OIC-Assistant Principal	17	6
OIC-Head Teacher	41	14
Teacher-in-Charge	24	8
Total	214	100

Level of Competence in terms of Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities. Found in Table 2 is the level of competence of the school heads when they are taken as a whole in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities. The data show that the school heads have the highest rating in terms of knowledge ($M=4.56$, $SD=0.45$), followed by skills ($M=4.47$, $SD=0.44$), and lastly, by abilities ($M=4.46$, $SD=0.63$). All the means, however, despite their differences, have a verbal interpretation of Very High Competence. Overall, the level of competence of the school heads is Very High, with a mean of 4.52 ($SD=0.41$).

Table 2. Level of Competence in terms of Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities of the School Heads when taken as a whole

Competence	M	SD	Interpretation
Knowledge	4.56	0.45	Very High Competence
Skills	4.47	0.44	Very High Competence
Abilities	4.46	0.63	Very High Competence
Overall Competence	4.52	0.41	Very High Competence
Scale: 4.25-5.00 Very High Competence 3.21-4.20 High Competence 2.61-3.20 Average Competence 1.81-2.60 Low Competence 1.00-1.81 Very Low Competence			

The Department of Education has set the qualification standards for school heads such as principals, head teachers, and teacher-in-charge to ensure that only individuals possessing the qualities needed for school leadership and management positions are appointed or designated. The school heads are passers of qualifying tests or the Principal's Examination given by the Department of Education. Moreover, the ranking for any school head position follows a set of criteria such as performance rating, experience, outstanding accomplishment, education and training, psychological attributes, and personality traits. Documents submitted should conform to Omnibus Rules on Appointments and other Human Resources Actions. These criteria and qualifying examinations explain the Very High Competence of the school heads.

School heads are managers and must possess the three basic skills of a manager. These are conceptual skills, technical and human skills (Newstrom, 2015). This result indicates that in the Philippine educational system, management/leadership positions are given to individuals with the necessary skills and level of competence.

Table 3 shows the level of competence in terms of knowledge of the school heads when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position.

The female group showed a higher rating ($M=4.62$) than the male group ($M=4.46$). The very high competence rating of the male and female school heads in terms of knowledge is not surprising.

When the respondents were grouped according to the school level, the data for their level of competence in terms of knowledge revealed that the school heads from the elementary level had a higher score ($M=4.57$) than the school heads from the secondary level ($M=4.52$). Both mean ratings are described as Very High Competence. The respondents with doctorate units group showed the highest score ($M=4.71$) among the three groups. Those with master's degrees garnered a score of 4.49, and those with doctorate degrees had the lowest score ($M=4.31$). All the mean ratings of the group are of very high competence. In terms of position, the group of principals has the highest score ($M=4.61$), followed by the OIC-Assistant Principal ($M=4.49$), next is the Teacher-in-Charge group ($M=4.47$), and last in the ranking is the OIC-Head Teachers ($M=4.40$).

School heads in the Philippines have been continuously trained in terms of school leadership and governance. The training is evident in the regular conduct of the School Head's Development Program, which is a series of training workshops, especially for newly promoted school heads. The training workshops are packaged as basic and advanced courses. Each package is usually conducted for two weeks, which is normally done in two separate venues. These training workshops allow the school heads to recalibrate their knowledge of how the theories should be applied in the field and how the recent programs of the Department should be effectively and efficiently implemented in the field. Moreover, the criteria for appointing a school head require compliance with the standard competencies for school heads. Thus, only those with qualifications, experience, and knowledge were selected for the position.

Table 3. Level of Competence in terms of Knowledge of the School Heads when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	4.46	Very High Competence
Female	4.62	Very High Competence
School Level		
Elementary	4.57	Very High Competence
Secondary	4.52	Very High Competence
Educational Background		
Master's degree	4.49	Very High Competence
With doctorate units	4.71	Very High Competence
Doctorate degree	4.31	Very High Competence
Position		
Principal	4.61	Very High Competence
OIC-Assistant Principal	4.49	Very High Competence
OIC-Head Teacher	4.40	Very High Competence
Teacher-in-Charge	4.47	Very High Competence
Overall Knowledge	4.56	Very High Competence

Table 4 shows the level of competence in terms of skills of the school heads when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position.

When school heads are grouped according to sex, the data revealed that the female group got a higher rating ($M=4.50$) compared to the male group ($M=4.42$), but both ratings are described as very high competence. In terms of the school level, the data showed that secondary-level school heads ($M=4.55$) got a higher score compared to elementary-level school heads ($M=4.46$). Considering the

educational background of the school heads, those with doctorate units ($M=4.60$) garnered the highest mean score, followed by school heads with master's degrees ($M=4.43$) and school heads with a doctorate degree ($M=4.18$) got the lowest mean score. In terms of their position, principals ($M=4.53$) got the highest mean score, securing the second spot are the Teachers-in-Charge ($M=4.42$), followed by the OIC-Assistant Principals ($M=4.31$) and the OIC-Head Teacher (4.27) landed in the last spot.

Table 4. Level of Competence in terms of Skills of the School Heads when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	4.42	Very High Competence
Female	4.50	Very High Competence
School Level		
Elementary	4.46	Very High Competence
Secondary	4.55	Very High Competence
Educational Background		
Master's degree	4.43	Very High Competence
With doctorate units	4.60	Very High Competence
Doctorate degree	4.18	Very High Competence
Position		
Principal	4.53	Very High Competence
OIC-Assistant Principal	4.31	Very High Competence
OIC-Head Teacher	4.27	Very High Competence
Teacher-in-Charge	4.42	Very High Competence
Overall Skills	4.47	Very High Competence

Table 5 shows the level of competence in terms of abilities of the school heads when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position.

Considering the sex, male ($M=4.47$) school heads got a higher mean score compared to female ($M=4.46$) school heads. When they are grouped according to the school level, secondary school heads ($M=4.49$) scored better than elementary school heads ($M=4.46$). In terms of educational background, school heads with doctorate units ($M=4.62$) garnered the highest mean score compared to school heads with master's degrees ($M=4.37$) and doctorate degrees ($M=4.25$). When the school heads are grouped according to position, principals ($M=4.51$) got the first spot, followed by OIC-Head Teachers ($M=4.49$) and Teachers-in-Charge (4.18), and last in the list are the OIC-Assistant Principals ($M=4.10$).

Table 5. Level of Competence in terms of Abilities of the School Heads when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	4.47	Very High Competence
Female	4.46	Very High Competence
School Level		
Elementary	4.46	Very High Competence
Secondary	4.49	Very High Competence
Educational Background		
Master's degree	4.37	Very High Competence
With doctorate units	4.62	Very High Competence
Doctorate degree	4.25	Very High Competence
Position		
Principal	4.51	Very High Competence
OIC-Assistant Principal	4.10	Very High Competence
OIC-Head Teacher	4.49	Very High Competence
Teacher-in-Charge	4.18	Very High Competence
Overall Abilities	4.46	Very High Competence

Acquired Needs of the School Heads in terms of Achievement, Power, and Affiliation. Table 6 shows the data regarding the acquired needs of school heads in terms of achievement, power, and affiliation.

When taken as a whole, the level of the acquired needs of the school heads in terms of power (M=4.65, SD=0.36), affiliation (M=4.51, SD=0.46), and achievement (M=4.31, SD=0.49) is very high.

Table 6. Acquired Needs of the School Heads in terms of Achievement, Power, and Affiliation when taken as a whole

Acquired Needs	M	SD	Interpretation
Power	4.65	0.36	Very High Need
Affiliation	4.51	0.46	Very High Need
Achievement	4.31	0.49	Very High Need
Scale: 4.25-5.00 Very High Need 3.21-4.20 High Need 2.61-3.20 Average Need 1.81-2.60 Low Need 1.00-1.81 Very Low Need			

Table 7 shows the data regarding the acquired needs of school heads in terms of power when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position.

When grouped according to sex, male (M=4.65) and female (M=4.65) school heads have garnered a very high need. In terms of their school level, elementary school heads (M=4.68) scored better than secondary school heads (M=4.64); both are interpreted as very high.

Considering the educational background of the school heads, doctorate units (M=4.81) scored the highest mean score compared to school heads with master's degrees (M=4.57) and doctorate degree holders (4.48). As indicated by their means, the school heads' need for power dominates the master's degree holders (M=4.57) and those with doctoral units (M=4.81). Both groups also need for affiliation as the second most dominant need, with a mean score of 4.47 and 4.56. The least dominant among the three acquired needs is the need for achievement, which is interpreted as a high need for master's degree holders (M=4.18) and a very high need for those who earned doctorate units (M=4.53). As observed, the doctorate holders need for affiliation as the most dominant with the highest mean among the three needs, followed by the need for power, both described as very high needs. Like the master's degree holders, the doctoral degree holders rated their need for achievement as high. Filipinos, by nature, are friendly and prefer peace and harmony not just at home but also in the workplace.

Furthermore, the quality of the relationship between the school head and the teachers is the latter's responsibility. Consequently, the school head felt a strong need for affiliation to engage with people under their supervision. Ahmed et al. (2017) found that the relationship between the employee and the supervisor influences employee performance and employee engagement.

Table 7. Acquired Needs of the School Heads in terms of power when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	4.65	Very High Need
Female	4.65	Very High Need
School Level		
Elementary	4.68	Very High Need
Secondary	4.64	Very High Need
Educational Background		
Master's degree	4.57	Very High Need
With doctorate units	4.81	Very High Need
Doctorate degree	4.48	Very High Need
Position		
Principal	4.68	Very High Need
OIC-Assistant Principal	4.78	Very High Need
OIC-Head Teacher	4.64	Very High Need
Teacher-in-Charge	4.38	Very High Need
Overall Power	4.65	Very High Need

Table 8 shows the data regarding the acquired needs of school heads in terms of affiliation when grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position.

Table 8. Acquired Needs of the School Heads in terms of affiliation when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	4.63	Very High Need
Female	4.64	Very High Need
School Level		
Elementary	4.62	Very High Need
Secondary	4.49	Very High Need
Educational Background		
Master's degree	4.47	Very High Need
With doctorate units	4.56	Very High Need
Doctorate degree	4.38	Very High Need
Position		
Principal	4.50	Very High Need
OIC-Assistant Principal	4.55	Very High Need
OIC-Head Teacher	4.58	Very High Need
Teacher-in-Charge	4.33	Very High Need
Overall Affiliation	4.51	Very High Need

Table 9 shows the data regarding the acquired needs of school heads in terms of achievement when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position.

Table 9. Acquired Needs of the School Heads in terms of achievement when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	4.25	Very High Need
Female	4.33	Very High Need
School Level		
Elementary	4.28	Very High Need
Secondary	4.31	Very High Need
Educational Background		
Master's degree	4.18	High Need
With doctorate units	4.53	Very High Need
Doctorate degree	4.00	High Need
Position		
Principal	4.32	Very High Need
OIC-Assistant Principal	4.46	Very High Need
OIC-Head Teacher	4.28	Very High Need
Teacher-in-Charge	4.08	High Need
Overall Achievement	4.31	Very High Need

School-Based Management (SBM) Level of Practice. Table 10 shows the data regarding the School-Based Management (SBM) Level of Practice in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources.

When taken as a whole ($M=2.39$, $SD=0.54$), the school heads' School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice is interpreted as best practice when considering leadership and governance ($M=2.43$, $SD=0.58$), accountability and continuous improvement ($M=2.36$, $SD=0.58$), management of resources ($M=2.45$, $SD=0.64$) as SBM principle, the school heads got an interpretation of best practice except for curriculum and instruction ($M=2.30$, $SD=0.54$) which is interpreted as the better practice of SBM.

Table 10. School-Based Management (SBM) Level of Practice of the School Heads, when taken as a whole

SBM Principle	M	SD	Interpretation
Leadership and Governance	2.43	0.58	Best
Curriculum and Instruction	2.30	0.54	Better
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.36	0.58	Best
Management of Resources	2.45	0.64	Best
Overall SBM Practice	2.39	0.54	Best

Scale: 2.35-3.00 Best 1.68-2.34 Better 1.00-1.67 Good

The indicator rated highest by the school heads is the management of resources, and the lowest is in curriculum and instruction. The results show that in the performance of the tasks based on the SBM framework of the Department of Education, the school heads gave more focus on the management of the school resources, such as monitoring of resource management processes, planning and programming of resources and ensuring the system for judicious and effective use of school resources. Moreover, they are also giving priority to their leadership and governance functions. Given that the SBM level of practice in terms of curriculum and instruction is better, it has to be given more

attention because, among the indicators, it is the one with the lowest rating. As educational leaders, school heads must be able to give priority to curriculum and instruction because it is the core business of all educational institutions.

Table 11 shows the results of the SBM Level of Practice of school heads in terms of leadership and governance.

Table 11. SBM Level of Practice in terms of Leadership and Governance when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	2.41	Best
Female	2.44	Best
School Level		
Elementary	2.09	Better
Secondary	2.36	Best
Educational Background		
Master's degree	2.27	Better
With doctorate units	2.57	Best
Doctorate degree	2.59	Best
Position		
Principal	2.48	Best
OIC-Assistant Principal	2.59	Best
OIC-Head Teacher	2.46	Best
Teacher-in-Charge	1.80	Better
Overall Leadership and Governance	2.43	Best

Table 12 shows the results of the SBM Level of Practice of school heads in terms of curriculum and instruction.

Table 12. SBM Level of Practice in terms of Curriculum and Instruction when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	2.40	Best
Female	2.34	Better
School Level		
Elementary	2.10	Better
Secondary	2.41	Best
Educational Background		
Master's degree	2.22	Better
With doctorate units	2.45	Best
Doctorate degree	2.58	Best
Position		
Principal	2.40	Best
OIC-Assistant Principal	2.37	Best
OIC-Head Teacher	2.45	Best
Teacher-in-Charge	1.83	Better
Overall Curriculum and Instruction	2.30	Better

Table 13 shows the results of the SBM Level of Practice of school heads in terms of accountability and continuous improvement.

Table 13. SBM Level of Practice in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	2.34	Better
Female	2.37	Best
School Level		
Elementary	1.98	Better
Secondary	2.44	Best
Educational Background		
Master's degree	2.18	Better
With doctorate units	2.47	Best
Doctorate degree	2.68	Best
Position		
Principal	2.40	Best
OIC-Assistant Principal	2.23	Better
OIC-Head Teacher	2.43	Best
Teacher-in-Charge	1.91	Better
Overall Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.36	Best

Table 14 shows the results of the SBM Level of Practice of school heads in terms of the management of resources.

Table 14. SBM Level of Practice in terms of Management of Resources when they are grouped according to sex, school level, educational background, and position

Variables	M	Interpretation
Sex		
Male	2.47	Best
Female	2.43	Best
School Level		
Elementary	2.05	Better
Secondary	2.53	Best
Educational Background		
Master's degree	2.27	Better
With doctorate units	2.59	Best
Doctorate degree	2.65	Best
Position		
Principal	2.47	Best
OIC-Assistant Principal	2.47	Best
OIC-Head Teacher	2.61	Best
Teacher-in-Charge	1.93	Better
Overall Management of Resources	2.45	Best

The difference in the Level of Competence. Table 15 shows the difference in the level of competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities when grouped according to sex and school level.

Considering knowledge as part of the school heads' competency, females (M=4.62) scored higher than their male (M=4.46) counterparts; thus, a significant difference was established. The level of competence in terms of knowledge of school heads was the same when the school level was considered.

Regarding the school heads' competency considering skills, sex as a variable was found to be significant. On the other hand, school level was found to be an insignificant variable. Considering the abilities of the school heads, both sex and school level have no significant difference when they are compared.

Table 15. The difference in the Level of Competence in terms of Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities of School Heads when they are grouped according to sex and school level

	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Knowledge	4.46	4.62	2.931*	296	0.004
	(0.45)	(0.45)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Knowledge	4.57	4.52	0.769	296	0.442
	(0.45)	(0.47)			
	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Skills	4.42	4.50	1.526	296	0.128
	(0.39)	(0.46)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Skills	4.46	4.55	4.459*	296	0.000
	(0.44)	(0.49)			
	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Abilities	4.47	4.46	0.283	296	0.778
	(0.43)	(0.71)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Abilities	4.46	4.49	0.408	296	0.684
	(0.47)	(1.10)			

Table 16 shows the difference in the level of competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities of school heads when they are grouped according to educational background and position

Regarding the school heads' level of competence in terms of knowledge, educational background (F=3.828, p=0.023) and position (F=3.166, p=0.000) have a significant difference. Considering their skills, both educational background (F=15.11, p=0.000) and position (F=5.341, p=0.001) were found to be significant variables. For the level of competency of school heads in terms of their abilities, a significant difference was established for educational background (F=16.30, p=0.000) and position (F=4.923, p=0.000) when they were compared.

Table 16. The difference in the Level of Competence in terms of Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities of School Heads when they are grouped according to educational background and position

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	F	p-value
Knowledge				
Educational Background				
Between groups	1.549	2	3.828*	0.023
Within groups	59.665	295		
Position				
Between groups	1.916	3	3.166*	0.000
Within groups	59.298	294		
Skills				
Educational Background				
Between groups	5.25	2	15.11*	0.000
Within groups	51.27	295		
Position				
Between groups	2.921	3	5.341*	0.001
Within groups	53.598	294		
Abilities				
Educational Background				
Between groups	11.76	2	16.30*	0.000
Within groups	106.40	295		
Position				
Between groups	5.652	3	4.923*	0.002
Within groups	112.503	294		

Table 17 shows the difference in the level of competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities of school heads when grouped according to sex and school level.

When considering sex and school level as the variable in comparing the means of the school heads' level of competence in terms of the need for achievement, affiliation, and achievement, school level ($t=3.205$, $p=0.001$) was the only significant variable considered for the need for affiliation of the school heads.

Table 17. The difference in the Acquired Needs of School Heads in terms of Need for Power, Affiliation, and Achievement when they are grouped according to sex and school level

Need for Achievement	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
	4.25	4.33	1.369	296	0.172
	(0.41)	(0.52)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
4.31	4.28	0.412	296	0.681	
(0.50)	(0.43)				
Need for Affiliation	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
	4.63	4.65	1.833	296	0.068
	(0.27)	(0.52)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
4.49	4.62	3.205*	296	0.001	
(0.45)	(0.47)				
Need for Power	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
	4.65	4.64	1.600	296	0.873
	(0.31)	(0.38)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
4.64	4.68	0.600	296	0.549	
(0.34)	(0.45)				

Table 18 shows the difference in the level of competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities of school heads when grouped according to educational background and position.

Considering the acquired needs of school heads in terms of the need for achievement, educational background ($F=29.00$, $p=0.000$) was found to have a significant difference when comparing means. For the need for power, both educational background ($F=32.10$, $p=0.000$) and position ($F=6.61$, $p=0.000$) has a significant difference in their means and were found to be significant variable considered in this study.

Table 18. The difference in the Acquired Needs of School Heads in terms of Need for Power, Affiliation, and Achievement when they are grouped according to educational background and position

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	F	p-value
Need for Achievement				
Educational Background				
Between groups	11.571	2	29.00*	0.000
Within groups	58.844	295		
Position				
Between groups	1.704	3	2.43	0.065
Within groups	68.711	294		
Need for Affiliation				
Educational Background				
Between groups	.634	2	1.492	0.227
Within groups	62.717	295		
Position				
Between groups	1.502	3	2.380	0.070
Within groups	61.849	294		
Need for Power				
Educational Background				
Between groups	6.778	2	32.10*	0.000
Within groups	31.146	295		
Position				
Between groups	2.397	3	6.61*	0.000
Within groups	35.527	294		

Table 19 shows the difference in the level of competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities of school heads when grouped according to sex and school level.

Comparing the means for curriculum and instruction has projected a significant difference in school heads' school level ($t=2.521$, $p=0.012$). Considering the accountability and continuous improvement indicator of the SBM level of practice of school heads, both sex ($t=2.197$, $p=0.029$) and school level ($t=5.552$, $p=0.000$) were found to be significant variables. On the other hand, for the management of resources as an indicator, both school level ($t=6.082$, $p=0.000$) and sex ($t=1.990$, $p=0.048$).

Table 19. The difference in the SBM Level of Practice of School Heads when they are grouped according to sex and school level

	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Leadership and Governance	2.27	2.40	1.980	296	0.028
	(0.39)	(0.60)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Leadership and Governance	2.20	2.38	0.998	296	0.044
	(0.50)	(0.43)			
	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Curriculum and Instruction	2.16	2.26	1.451	296	0.148
	(0.42)	(0.59)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Curriculum and Instruction	2.04	2.26	2.521*	296	0.012
	(0.45)	(0.47)			
	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.23	2.36	2.197*	296	0.029
	(0.42)	(0.62)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	1.89	2.39	5.552*	296	0.000
	(0.54)	(0.53)			
	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Management of Resources	2.30	2.45	1.990*	296	0.048
	(0.47)	(0.69)			
	School Level		t	df	p-value
	Elementary	Secondary			
Management of Resources	1.91	2.49	6.082*	296	0.000
	(0.69)	(0.57)			

Table 20 shows the difference in the level of competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and abilities of school heads when grouped according to educational background and position.

Considering the educational background and position of school heads in comparing means of their SBM level of practice, all SBM indicators have significant differences, and both variables were found to be significant.

A significant difference in the educational background ($F=20.68$, $p=0.000$) and position ($F=4.23$, $p=0.006$) in terms of leadership and governance was established, and the same results were observed for curriculum and instruction [educational background ($F=13.98$, $p=0.000$) and position ($F=3.181$, $p=0.024$)]. The difference in accountability and continuous improvement was significant regarding their educational background with $F=22.00$ ($p=0.000$) and position with $F=2.979$ ($p=0.032$). The management of resources indicator has a significant difference in comparing the means of the school heads [educational background ($F=11.11$, $p=0.000$) and position ($F=7.249$, $p=0.000$)].

Table 20. The difference in the SBM Level of Practice of School Heads when they are grouped according to educational background and position

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	F	p-value
Leadership and Governance				
Educational Background				
Between groups	10.770	2	20.68*	0.000
Within groups	73.675	295		
Position				
Between groups	3.633	3	4.23*	0.006
Within groups	80.812	294		
Curriculum and Instruction				
Educational Background				
Between groups	7.402	2	13.98*	0.000
Within groups	75.699	295		
Position				
Between groups	2.692	3	3.181*	0.024
Within groups	80.408	294		
Accountability and Continuous Improvement				
Educational Background				
Between groups	11.973	2	22.00*	0.000
Within groups	76.726	295		
Position				
Between groups	2.734	3	2.979*	0.032
Within groups	85.965	294		
Management of Resources				
Educational Background				
Between groups	8.223	2	11.11*	0.000
Within groups	105.813	295		
Position				
Between groups	8.084	3	7.249*	0.000
Within groups	105.952	294		

Table 21 shows the significant relationship between the school heads' competency, acquired needs, and SBM Practice.

The school heads' level of competency is significantly related to their level of acquired needs ($r=.595$, $p=0.000$) and SBM level of practice ($r=.381$, $p=0.000$). Moreover, their level of acquired needs also showed a significant relationship with their SBM level of practice ($r=.453$, $p=0.000$). The results imply that the higher the level of competencies of the school heads and their level of acquired needs, the higher their SBM level of practice. School heads with the needed knowledge, skills, and abilities are motivated to perform the tasks in the SBM framework. Vroom's Expectancy theory explains the findings. According to the theory, an individual will be motivated to perform better about the expectations; expectancy is affected by having the right skills to perform the job, availability of resources, and necessary support. In developing this theory, Vroom realized that performance is based on individual factors such as skills, knowledge, experience, and abilities.

Table 21. Relationship of the Competency, Acquired Needs, and SBM Practice of School Heads

Variables	Acquired Needs	SBM
Competency	r-value	.593**
	p-value	0.000
	Interpretation	Significant
Acquired Needs	r-value	.453**
	p-value	0.000
	Interpretation	Significant

CONCLUSION

School heads in the Division of Iloilo possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities to perform their functions as educational leaders.

Generally, school heads have strong power, affiliation, and achievement needs. The Need for Power or the desire to make their subordinates behave in a way they would not have behaved otherwise

dominates over the desire to be friendly and have close interpersonal relationships and the desire to excel.

School heads can perform their functions concerning the practice of School-Based Management satisfactorily in terms of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources.

Among the factors considered determinants of the school heads' competencies, cutting across the three forms of competencies, are their position and educational background. However, other factors affect the school heads' competency in terms of knowledge, such as the sex and school level of the school heads.

Factors such as position/designation affect the need for achievement of the school heads, while on the other hand, sex and educational background affect the need for the power of the school heads.

Factors that affect the SBM Level of Practice of the school heads vary depending on the SBM indicator. However, there are factors, the majority are personal, which consistently affects the SBM Level of Practice across indicators. These factors are the school level and the educational background of the school heads. Finally, the school heads' competencies, acquired needs and SBM practice are all related.

REFERENCES

- Abulencia, A. S. (2012). School-based management: A structural reform intervention. *Philippine Normal University Journal on Teacher Education*, 44-67.
- Ahmed, S., Ahmad, F. B., & Jaaffar, A. R. (2017). Employee engagement on employee relations with supervisor and employee performance relationship in developing economy: Critical analysis with PLSSEM. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 2(4), 389-398.
- Aniemeka, I., Agbodike, F., & Ewuim, N. (2013). Conflict management in organization: Gender perspective. *Review of Public Administration & Management*, 1(2), 51-60.
- Bandur, A. (2012). School-based management developments: challenges and impacts. *Journal of educational administration*.
- Cabardo, J. R. O. (2016). Levels of Participation of the School Stakeholders to the Different School-Initiated Activities and the Implementation of School-Based Management. *Journal of Inquiry and Action in Education*, 8(1), 81-94.
- Carr-Hill, R., Rolleston, C., Schendel, R., & Waddington, H. (2018). The effectiveness of school-based decision making in improving educational outcomes: a systematic review. *Journal of Development Effectiveness*, 10(1), 61-94.
- Cayubitt, R. F. O., Cadacio, C. A. D., Chua, M. P. T. O., Faeldon, V. A. H., Go, W. P., & Verdan, M. K. C. (2016). Academic delay of gratification, academic achievement, and need for affiliation of selected high school students. *Educational Measurement and Evaluation Review*, 7(2), 1-14.
- Chaubey, D. S., Mishra, N., & Dimri, R. P. (2017). Analysis of employee relationship management and its impact on job satisfaction. *Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce*, 8(2), 15-25.
- Department of Education. (2015). School-based management from <http://www.deped.gov.ph/orders/do-45-s-2015>.
- Durban, J. M., & Catalan, R. D. (2012). Issues and concerns of Philippine education through the years. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 1(2), 61-69.
- Elmazi, E. (2018). The role of principal's power and teacher empowerment. *European Scientific Journal*, 18(43), 1867-7881.
- Elmelegy, R. I. (2015). School-based management: An approach to decision-making quality in Egyptian general secondary schools. *School Leadership & Management*, 35(1), 79-96.

Ilagan, J. R., Hechanova, M. R., Co, T., & Pleyto, V. (2014). Bakit ka kumakayod? Developing a Filipino needs theory of motivation. *Philippine journal of psychology*, 47(1), 117-143.

Jha, S. (2010). Need for growth, achievement, power and affiliation: Determinants of psychological empowerment. *Global Business Review*, 11(3), 379-393.

Kuluchumila, R. C. (2014). Preparation and development of secondary school heads: What should be done in Tanzania. *British Journal of Education*, 2(2), 9-39.

Melnikova, J. (2013). The holistic model of capability of Lithuanian school heads: Theoretical framework and empirical evidence. *Socialiniai tyrimai*, (2), 13-23.

Sutherland, I. E., & Yoshida, R. K. (2015). Communication competence and trust in leaders. *Journal of School Leadership*, 25(6), 1039-1063.

Vicera, C. R., & Bantor, S. S. (2013). Empowerment of School Heads and School-Based Management Implementation in the Public Secondary Schools. *Journal of Society and Technology*, 3(1), 71-75.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.